

EPHAR2024

The Federation of European Pharmacological Societies

9th European Congress of Pharmacology

23-26
June
2024

**ATHENS
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Megaron Athens
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ephar2024.org

**ABSTRACT
BOOK**

PP187. Bile acids upregulate carbonyl reductase and aldo-keto reductase expression in breast adenocarcinoma cell line following doxorubicin treatment

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Introduction: Carbonyl reductase (CBR) and aldo-keto reductase (AKR) are involved in the NADPH-dependent two-electron reduction of the anticancer drug doxorubicin into the less active and cardiotoxic metabolite doxorubicinol. As endogenous signaling molecules, bile acids have a propensity to modulate the gene expression of numerous drug-metabolizing enzymes. The aim of the study was to assess the influence of bile acids, ursodeoxycholic (UDCA) and chenodeoxycholic acid (CDCA) on the expression of CBR1 and AKR1A1 in the breast adenocarcinoma MCF7 cell line.

Methods: Human breast adenocarcinoma MCF7 cells were treated with 0.25 μ M (D) or co-treated with doxorubicin and either 50 μ M of ursodeoxycholic acid (DU) or 6 μ M of chenodeoxycholic acid (DC). Following 24 hours, cells were harvested, and RNA was isolated and transcribed into cDNA. The expression of CBR and AKR1A1 mRNA was assessed using RT-qPCR compared to β -actin as a reference gene. Gene expression was analyzed using the comparative $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ method, and the data were analyzed by one-way Anova and Tuckey's post-hoc test.

Results: The expression of AKR1A1 in D group increased 1.1 fold compared to untreated cells. Expression of AKR1A1 was upregulated in DU group (11.49 \pm 1.83 fold vs. control $p < 0.001$; 10.65 \pm 1.69 fold vs. D $p < 0.001$) and in DC group (27.91 \pm 3.58 fold vs. control $p < 0.001$; 25.86 \pm 3.31 fold vs. D $p < 0.001$). CBR1 expression in D group increased 2.78 \pm 0.59 fold vs. the control ($p = 0.946$). Co-treatment with ursodeoxycholic acid reduced CBR1 expression compared to group D (-1.57 \pm 0.34 $p = 0.56$) whereas CBR1 was upregulated in DC group (14.38 \pm 5.72 vs. control, $p < 0.001$ and 5.23 \pm 2.08 vs. D, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusions: By upregulating the expression of CBR1 and AKR1A1, chenodeoxycholic and ursodeoxycholic may affect the therapeutic efficacy of doxorubicin by metabolizing the parent compound into an inactive metabolite.

Acknowledgements: Supported by the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technological Development, Republic of Serbia, Grant III41012, and Project of Special Interest for Sustainable Development in the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Grant 142-451-3522/2023-01.